

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B326
Date: 12 September 2007
Take Off 08:32:31
Landing: 13:52:49
Flight Time 5h 20m 18s

Campaign: CAESAR

Operating Area: SW approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
3	CCM 1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Stuart Newman	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Core Chem / CCM2 / AVAPS	Steve Devereau	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Shims SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
9	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
10	Mission Scientist 2	Andreas Keil	Met Office
11	MARSS	Dave Pollard	Met Office
12	TAFTS	Paul Green	Imperial
13			
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15			
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Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B326
 Date: 12 September 2007
 Project: CAESAR
 Location: SW approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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080312		cgps	-.07 kft	126	b326cgps.log
080321		inu	-.07 kft	126	to nav
080329		GIN	-.07 kft	126	on
082518		heimann	-.07 kft	126	close
082528		bbr	-.07 kft	126	extend
082818		asp	-.06 kft	176	open
083231		T/O	-.08 kft	212	Cranfield
083337		heimann	1.2 kft	309	open
084433		nev	10.0 kft	240	zero
084541		jw	10.0 kft	241	zero
084624		twc	10.0 kft	249	power cycled
084716		heimann	10.0 kft	246	cal08
085821		video	18.0 kft	298	#1 UP, #2Forward start
090934		bbr	18.0 kft	254	retract
091330	093234	Profile 1	18.0 - -.41 kft	252	50ft
091353		bbr	17.7 kft	252	extend
092515		entering cloud	6.1 kft	292	
092629		clear	4.9 kft	294	
093255		bbr	-.36 kft	357	retract
093520	094518	Run 1.1	-.35 - -.28 kft	221	
093534		heimann	-.34 kft	220	cal09
093553		nev	-.30 kft	220	zero
094711	101353	Profile 2	-.36 - 24.0 kft	029	
094741		bbr	0.03 kft	030	extend
095849		p2	10.9 kft	027	interrupt
100039		p2	11.0 kft	164	restart
101450		bbr	24.0 kft	244	retract
101542		heimann	24.0 kft	330	cal06
101614		TWC	24.0 kft	350	status flashing -28C
101753	102755	Run 2.1	23.1 - 23.0 kft	348	
101828		heimann	23.0 kft	347	cal05
101902		nev	23.0 kft	347	zero
102300		Sonde 1	23.0 kft	347	
102557		video	23.0 kft	347	#1 now up, #2 now dow
102953	103946	Run	23.1 - 23.0 kft	165	r2.2
104007		heimann	23.0 kft	194	cal05
104044		nev	23.0 kft	257	zero
104136	105138	Run 2.3	23.0 kft	342	
105352	105528	Orbit 1	23.1 - 23.0 kft	222	240M start 51' rhd
105648	105832	Orbit 2	23.1 - 23.0 kft	282	290M 51' rhd
105931	110047	Orbit 3	23.0 - 22.6 kft	007	00
110132		!	23.3 kft	013	update fltsumm restarted
110400	110525	Profile 3	25.0 kft	167	
110808	111523	Run 3.1	25.0 kft	166	start 11:05:25
110901		!	25.0 kft	166	all fm pc windows applications restarted
111723	112402	Profile 4	25.0 - 30.0 kft	347	
112337		p4	30.1 kft	357	interrupt
112403	113045	run 4.1	30.0 kft	356	
112518		heimann	30.0 kft	354	cal04
113351	113947	Profile 5	30.0 - 33.0 kft	179	
113947	114949	Run 5.1	33.0 kft	176	
114147		heimann	33.0 kft	176	cal04
114531		nev	33.0 kft	176	zero
115149	120249	Run 5.2	33.0 kft	347	
115842		Sonde 2	33.0 kft	346	
120147		video	33.0 kft	347	#5 UP, #6 DOWN start
120505	121524	Run 5.3	33.0 kft	175	
120910		Sonde 3	33.0 kft	175	
121747	122215	Profile 6	33.1 - 29.0 kft	348	

122215	123217	Run 6.1	29.0 kft	348
123423	124032	Profile 7	29.1 - 23.1 kft	178
124033	125045	Run 7.1	23.0 kft	175
125233	125600	Run 7.2	23.0 kft	357
125342		heimann	23.0 kft	359 cal07
125409		nev	23.0 kft	359 zero
125613	125755	Orbit 4	23.1 kft	025 040M 50' rhd
125818	125959	Orbit 5	23.1 - 23.0 kft	074 100M 50' rhd
130215		!	23.0 kft	053 end of science
135249		Land	-.06 kft	212 Cranfield

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B326 Track 12-SEP-07

Sortie Brief

Option 1: CAESAR Radiative properties of cirrus

B326 12/09/07
T/O 09:30 L (0830Z)

Aim:

The aim of this sortie is to determine the radiative properties of frontal or convective cirrus using multiple frequencies from the range of remote sensing instruments on the aircraft. For closure it is also important to determine the in-situ properties of the cloud and to make radiative measurements of the atmosphere above and below the cirrus. To obtain in-situ vertical distributions either perform profile ascents and descents, or a Lagrangian spiral descent if the cirrus is extensive and homogenous. Measurements should be made advecting with the wind, such that the same airmass is continuously measured.

Straight and level runs should be made below, above and in the cirrus. Over the sea a 100ft run will be required to measure the SST. Orbits are to be made below the cloud with SWS viewing upwards to determine the phase function of the ice particles.

Satellite Overpasses:

Metop (IASI) 1025Z
AQUA (AIRS) 1339Z

Weather conditions:

Convective, frontal or Lee wave cirrus. Clear sky below the cirrus in the measurement area is essential. Ideally the cirrus should not extend above 35,000ft.

Locations:

Over sea.

Instruments required:

Critical: ARIES, SWS, SID2, 2DC, Temp, Humidity (incl FWVS), AVAPS

Desirable: MARSS, TAFTS, SHIMS, CPI, SID1, FFSSP, 2DP, CIPs, Heimann, Core chem (auto mode OK)

Mission scientist's debrief for CAESAR flight B326 on 12 Sept 2007

S. M. Newman

Summary:

This CAESAR flight was conducted in conjunction with a MetOp overpass, with an Aqua overpass occurring shortly after the end of science. This science was complicated by extensive stratocumulus capped by an inversion near the surface which was persistent, and the cirrus was too high to get above. Nevertheless TAFTS worked well early in the sortie to give coincident cirrus measurements with ARIES.

Although the forecast was for cirrus above an otherwise clear sky column, the actual conditions found in the area of operations was extensive Sc (between 5500-6500 ft on descent to the surface). An initial run at 100 feet for SST characterisation was carried out, but it became increasingly clear that there were very few clear slots in the Sc layer. It was decided to continue with the sortie on the basis of operating over uniform Sc (i.e. radiative transfer modelling will have to account for this as the emitting surface). Unfortunately there was not time to fit in a run just above the Sc for radiometric characterisation.

An ascent was made to FL230 where a reasonably uniform cirrus layer was identified with a base at around FL240. Over a large area the Sc was extensive below. A dropsonde was released at 1023Z in order to coincide with the MetOp overpass at 1025Z. It became apparent that the cirrus was better (or, at least, thicker) at the northern end of the operating area, close to the Irish FIR boundary. This persisted for the whole sortie despite prevailing winds from the north advecting the cloud south. A second run at FL230 was followed by three orbits, at 50° (twice) and 60° to get good SWS data.

A profile ascent to FL250 was made to operate just above cloud base; there was quite low thickness between the aircraft and the surface which meant the underlying Sc was visible at times. Low concentrations of small ice (100 µm) were seen. The aircraft weight with a heavy fuel load was not conducive to rapid ascent, but a run at FL300 was carried where it became evident that the highest cirrus was too high to reach (in excess of FL350). Further runs at FL330 were carried out above most of the cloud, with thinnish cirrus above. The northern portions of the runs exhibited extensive cirrus with Sc below, whereas in the south the cirrus was very thin or non-existent and the Sc was broken or there were even patches of clear sky to the surface. (Sc burn-off due to insolation under clear skies?) Two dropsondes were released at FL330. During the third run at this level the 146 actually intercepted its own contrail from the previous run.

A run at FL290 was made to be midway between cloud top and base; cloud physics reported bullet rosettes on the 2D probes. A final run-and-a-bit was carried out at FL230 below the cloud base, with two orbits at a bank angle of 50°.

Instruments:

SWS, ARIES and MARSS worked fine. Deimos data will need looking at. TAFTS worked at "5/10", with good data at the beginning of the sortie but deteriorating later. The flight manager reported that the Total Water heaters were failing.

B326 12/09/07

	Time Z	Manoeuvre	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	0830Z	Takeoff from Cranfield & Transit at appropriate level to enter operating area at min altitude	50	50
2	0920Z	Straight and level run of 10 mins duration at 100 ft over sea only.	10	60
3	0930Z	Profile ascent from min altitude to 1000ft below cirrus base at 1000ft/min (interrupted when necessary)	35	95
4	1005Z	Fly 3 straight and level reciprocal runs 1000ft below cirrus, orientated across wind, each of 10 mins. Drop 1 sonde just before the 1025Z overpass.	35	130
5	1040Z	Fly two orbits below cloud at SZA (or max) banking angle	10	140
6	1050Z	Profile ascent to 1000ft above cirrus base	5	145
7	1055Z	Fly one straight and level run in cloud, orientated across wind, of 10 mins	10	155
8	1105Z	Profile ascent to 1000ft below cirrus top	10	165
9	1115Z	Fly one straight and level run in cloud, orientated across wind, of 10 mins	10	175
10	1125Z	Profile ascent to 1000ft above cirrus top	5	180
11	1130Z	Fly three straight and level reciprocal runs 1000ft above cirrus, orientated across wind, each of 10 mins. Drop between 1 and 2 sondes during one run, ideally during 1339Z satellite overpass	35	215
12	1205Z	EITHER Perform a Lagrangian spiral descent at 2 ms ⁻¹ , advecting with the wind, to 1000ft below cirrus base if operating area is extensive, then go to 16	25	240
12	1205Z	OR Profile descent to level approx. half way between cloud top and base	5	220
13	1210Z	Fly 1 or 2 straight and level runs 1000ft in cloud, orientated across wind, of 10 mins	10	230
14	1220Z	Profile descent to 1000ft below cloud base	10	240
15	1230Z	Fly one straight and level run 1000ft below cirrus base, orientated across wind, of 10 mins.	10	250
16	1240Z	Perform one orbit at SZA (or max) banking angle	5	255
17	1245Z	Profile descent to transit altitude	10	265
18	1255Z	Transit to Cranfield	50	315
19	1345Z	Land		

Metop Overpass

METOP-A 2007/09/12 UTC METOP-A ORBITAL PREDICT PLOT EPOCH DATE: 07/08/30
■ lat: 51.15 lon: 358.57 res: 9 km

AQUA Overpass:

AQUA 2007/09/12 AQUA ORBITAL PREDICT PLOT / EPOCH DATE: 07/08/30
■ lat: 51.15 slon: 358.57 AIRS swath angle: 47.3 deg res: 9 km

Instrument operator instructions:

Nev

- when out of cloud in a straight and level run zero it

ARIES and SWS

- Both instruments must point in the same direction (either zenith or nadir) as each other, except during cal. ARIES needs to tell SWS where it is pointing.
- Majority of time should be towards the cloud (or sea at 100ft) , however, still need some data pointing away to characterise the atmosphere above and below the cloud (e.g. ~2 of 10 min run)
- For orbits both instruments should view towards cloud for whole time
- When close to the area of operation (~15mins) take data during both transits

ARIES

- If it is still unstable for zenith views (shutter open) at high altitudes, it is better to get 1 min of good data in a 10 min run (with rest of time with shutter closed viewing calcs or nadir) than all bad data – let SWS know which viewing direction and when.

SWS

- Continue to take data during the profiles
- Ensure that the signal does not saturate. Request extra orbits if necessary.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST: STUART NEWMAN

CAESAR SW APPROACHES

Flight No **B.326**.....

Date **12/9/2007**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
083235					TAKE-OFF
0840					Moist on ascent to 820 mls then drier layer
0848	Transit	FL100	245	52°N 130°W	Wind 7ms ⁻¹ /33i° T 3.5°C Td -18.9°C
09107	"	FL180	251	51°42' 312°W	Over uniform Sc over S. Wales, patchy Cirrus and Contrails above
091330	P1	FL180 ↓	252	51°30' 3°S4'	
092010	"	FL113	253	51°18' 4°42'	Wind 6ms ⁻¹ /286° T 1.0°C Td -13°C Still uniform Sc below, patchy Ci above
0925	"	6500 ft	291	51°24' 5°12'	Tops of Sc
0926	"	5500 ft	294	51°24' 5°18'	Base of Sc; few marine Cu below
0929	"	3000 ft	355	51°30' 5°30'	In cloud at times but tenous
093230		Soft		51°48' 5°30'	Calm sea state, no whitecaps
093520	R1.1	100 ft	220	51°42' 5°42'	THeimann x 16.5°C
094030	"	"	220	5°30' 6°W	9ms ⁻¹ /56° wind T 17.2°C Td 14°C
094515	end R1.1				Some breaks in Sc above, but few, still nearly 8/8
094710	P2	100 ft ↑			260 max PCASP
095330		6000 ft	030	51°42' 6°6'	In gap between cloud layers
095430		7000 ft	027	51°42' 6°W	Emerging from cloud tops T 8.6°C Td -15°C
					Strong inversion capping marine cloud Sc layer
0959	Interr- upt	FL110			Interupt for turn, Sc layer stretches as far as eye
100039	Resume	FL110 ↑		51°34' 5°42'	Cirrus ahead to south looks more substantial so heading for that
100820		FL186 ↑	165	51°24' 5°30'	Windsight 7ms ⁻¹ /327° T -14° Td -23°C Still quite dry at this level
101340		FL240		5° 59' 8"	At or near base of surrounding cirrus patches so choosing this level for first run
1016					Revision: better choice FL230 below the base; heading north over Sc
101752	R2.1	FL230	347	51°6' 5°24'	
1019					Variations in Ci thickness above
1022					Thicker above

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.326**
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 Date 12/9/07

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
102300					Dropsonde release
1024					Cameras switched to up+down 2D saw graupel briefly
102630	(R2.1)	F230	347	51°48' S°36'	Thicker Ci above, uniform Sc below
102750	end R2.1	"			Turning on reciprocal
102945	R2.2	F230	164	51°54' S°30'	Definitely thicker Ci at this northern end of area T-25°C Td-29°C
1031					2D reports occasional particles
1035	(R2.2)	F230	166	51°24' S°18'	Few breaks in Sc below to starboard, Ci looks a bit thinner above
1037					MARSS reports lower BTs for downwelling WV channels, consistent with thinner Ci
103945	end R2.2	F230			Looks like southerly edge of Ci coincides with end of run and turn
104134	R2.3	F230	342	51°8' S°18'	Significantly below cirrus+contrails just ahead
105140	end R2.3				
105350	01	F230	240-		SZA ~50° angle of bank 50°
105530	end 01				
105649	02	F230	290-		50° bank, fairly uniform Ci by eye
105835	end 02	"			SWS saturated, so repeating at 60°
105930	03	F230			Had to ease off bank angle mid-orbit
1105~	R3.1	F250	167	51°36' S°36'	In cloud run S-60 particles/d (can still see the Sc below)
1114					Cloud thinning both above + below
111520	end R3.1	F250			
111721	P4	F250↑			2D reports we are in a clear slot
112325	Inter-upt				
112345	R4.1	F300	355	51°30' S°42'	Restricted by air traffic to this level
1125		F300			Some evidence of layering in cirrus, we appear to be nearer top
1128					Between layers here? Low concs of small ice 10/litre 100µm
113045	end 4.1				Run curtailed by air traffic

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.326**
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 Date **12/9/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
113349	P5	F2300 ↑	178	51°34' S 30°	Some cloud above too high to reach, estimated F2350 or more
					TAFS lost fringes during orbits and data quality was reduced
113945	end P5 RS.1	F2330	176	51°24' S 30°	
1147					We seem to be in clear air here and only broken Sc below
114945	end RS.1	F2330			This southerly end clear below + above
115149	RS.2	F2330	346	50°24' S 30°	
115630			348	50°48' S 42'	Now in cirrus, Sc below with a few breaks
115839					Dropsonde release
120000		F2330	348	51°12' S 48'	Reasonably homogeneous Sc below
1201					100 particles/cc 2D at times, variable
1202		F2330		51°18' S 48'	Only v. thin cirrus above Definitely best conditions here at north
120503	RS.3	"	174		
120906					Dropsonde release, still in cirrus
1212					Our own contrail visible just to right we will cross it
121330					In our contrail from previous run
121420					Out of contrail
121522	end RS.3	F2330			Not much cloud at this end
122212	R6.1	FL290	348	50°54' S 48'	In-cloud run
122430		"			Slightly broken Sc below, variable thickness Ci above
1227					2D reports bullet rosettes on this run currently in thinish patch
1230		F2290	349	51°36' W	Blanket Sc below T -39 Td -40°C Winds 2ms ¹ /345°
123216	end R6.1				
123422	P7	FL290 ↓	176	51°42' S 54'	
124031	R7.1	FL230	175	51°12' S 48'	Breaks in Sc below, seem to be below cirrus
1245					Largely clear below but cirrus above

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Next
M/S 2

Flight No **B.326**.....
FAAM © 2004

Date 12/9/07.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	CAESAR	Flight		SW Approaches	
					→ NW winds
					→ Ci about 24k - 32k, largely cloud free below expected
~~~~~					
8:32				Cranfield	V/O
9:30				of the coast of S-wales	→ F/P to P/P Sc (obscure inversion) ↓ forced to use Sc as "surface" → excellent Ci → Ci heights: ≈ 24k - ≈ 32k ft → all instruments OK
10:20					SONDE dropped (Metop ^{≈ coinciding with} <del>orphan</del> )
11:22		30k			multi-layered clouds appear
11:45		33k			146 - contours constantly at this level
11:58		33k ft			SONDE
12:05					SONDE
12:55					no Sc below (max 1/8) during last 2 orbits
13:00					End of Science
13:				Cranfield	Landing

# CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 326

Date: 07:15:00	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
08:40:00																SID1 out of Sync restarted (B326-3.SRD)	
09:13:30	1	0.05	2		Noise											Start Profile 1 from FL180	
09:14:33	2	0.07			Noise											FL170	
09:15:39	4	0.07			Noise											FL160	
09:16:35	6	0.07			Noise											FL150	
09:17:34	8	0.07			Noise											FL140	
09:18:35	7	0.07			Noise											FL130	
09:19:37	20	0.11		10	2											FL120	
09:20:35	40	0.10		15	1											FL110	
09:21:20	45	0.11		20	2											FL100 Noise occ on FFSSP and PCASP	
09:22:23	45	0.10	3	20	2											FL090	
09:23:24	50	0.08		2	1											FL080	
09:24:30	30	0.08	3	1	1											FL070	
09:25:19	70	0.10	122	100	10											FL060	
09:26:19	110	0.08	135	10	1											FL050	
09:27:22	110	0.08	136	10	1											FL040	
09:28:25	150	0.08		15	1											FL030	
09:29:23	150	0.08		20	2											FL020	
09:30:28	180	0.08		20	1											FL010	
09:32:33	350	0.08	137	40	1											End of Profile 1 @ 50'	
09:35:21																Start Run 1 @ 100'	
09:36:00	330	0.08	139	20	1												
09:38:00	260	0.08	141	15	1											Lots of noise on FFSSP and PCASP	
09:40:00	500	0.07	142	15	1												
09:42:00	300	0.07	143	15	1												
09:44:00	285	0.07	146	15	1												
09:45:10																End of Run 1	
09:47:20																Start Profile 2 from 100'	
09:48:49	260	0.08														FL010	
09:49:55	120	0.08	155	10	1											FL020	
09:51:46	90	0.08	157	10	1											FL040	
09:52:53	70	0.08	158	10	1											FL050	
09:53:57	60	0.08	234	1000	2000											FL060	
09:54:52	20	0.08	429	10	20											FL070	
09:55:54	10	0.07			Noise											FL080	
09:56:57	10	0.07		5	2											FL090	
09:57:56	10	0.07		5	Noise											FL100	
09:59:04	5	0.07														FL110	
10:01:48	4	0.07			Noise											FL120	
10:02:50	3	0.07														FL130	
10:03:50	4	0.07		3	1											FL140	
10:04:50	4	0.08														FL150	
10:05:43	4	0.07														FL160	

PCASP Reference Volts = 9.3V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.4V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.17V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.0 cc/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.0V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.06V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 12mw	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = -3.2V		

# CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 326

**Date: 07:15:00**    **Operator: MAP**    **DRS Time: +0**    **DAU1 Time: +0**    **DAU2 Time: +0**    **DAU3 Time: +0**    **Aux1 Time: +0**    **Aux2 Time: +0**    **Page 2 of 2**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:06:50	2	0.06	429													FL170	
10:07:51	5	0.05														FL180	
10:08:53	3	0.07														FL190	
10:09:54	3	0.07														FL200	
10:10:54	4	0.08		1												FL210	
10:11:51	2	0.08														FL220	
10:12:57	4	0.06														FL230	
10:13:55	3	0.08														End of Profile 2 @ FL240	
10:17:54																Start Run 2.1 @ FL230	
10:18:00	3	0.08	430	2	1												
10:20:00	3	0.07		2	1												
10:22:00	5	0.07		3	2	1	200								10		
10:24:00	4	0.06		1	3												
10:26:00	5	0.06		10	10	5	150	25							10		
10:27:54																End of Run 2.1 @ FL230	
10:29:50																Start Run 2.2 @ FL230	
10:30:00	5	0.13	432	10	10	15	150	15	100						10		
10:32:00	35	0.12	433	20	5	2	275	800	200						10		
10:34:00	2	0.06		10	1	35	225	100	200						10		
10:36:00	1	0.05	434	1	1												
10:38:00	2	0.07		1													
10:39:45																End of Run 2.2	
10:41:36																Start Run 2.3 @ FL230	
10:42:00	3	0.07		1	1												
10:44:00	1	0.06		1				Noise									
10:46:00	3	0.08		10	10	10	250	Noise							10		
10:48:00	2	0.06		1	Noise			Noise									
10:50:00	8	0.08		50	Noise	20	250	Noise									
10:51:40																End of Run 2.3	
10:53:52																Start Orbits	
11:00:53																End of Orbits	
11:03:32	3	0.08	443	10	10	15	200	Noise							10	Start Profile 3 from FL230	
11:05:30	8	0.07	444	20	20	12	200	Noise							10	FL240	
11:05:27	8	0.10		20	10	15	200	Noise							10	End of Profile 3 & Start Run 3.1 @ FL250	
11:06:00	4	0.25	445	20	5	15	200	Noise							10		
11:08:00	5	0.07	446	20	2	30	300	Noise							10		
11:10:00	5	0.07	447	100	10	35	300	Noise							10		
11:12:00	5	0.17	449	80	40	10	400	Noise							10		
11:14:00	2	0.07	450	30	3												
11:15:22																End of Run 3.1	
11:17:24																Start Profile 4 from FL250	
11:18:33	2	0.05	451	15	1	3										FL260	
11:19:35	8	0.14	452	10	2	2	350	Noise								FL270	

PCASP Reference Volts = 9.3V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.4V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.17V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.0 cc/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.0V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.06V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 12mw	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = -3.2V		

# CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 326

Date: 07:15:00	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:20:36	1	0.06	452	15	2	10	175	Noise							10	FL280	
11:21:45	20	0.17	453	20	5	15	300	Noise							10	FL290	
11:23:25	1	0.07	454	100	10	70	175	Noise							10	End of Profile 4 & Start Run 4.1 @ FL300	
11:24:00	1	0.06	455	10	10	6	100	Noise							11		
11:26:00	1	0.07	456	10	15	20	100	Noise							11		
11:28:00	1	0.13	457	20	10	15	100	Noise							11		
11:30:00	10	0.07	458	5	Noise	3	75	Noise							11		
11:30:45																End of Run 4.1	
11:33:52																Start Profile 5 from FL300	
11:35:30	10	0.11	461	150	60	45	100	Noise							11	FL310	
11:37:45	1	0.09	463	100	10	35	125	Noise							10	FL320	
11:39:49																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 5.1 @ FL330	
11:40:00	5	0.07	464	20	5	15	175	Noise							10		
11:42:00	1	0.15	465	200	10	15	150	Noise							10		
11:44:00	5	0.11	467	80	8	1											
11:46:00	2	0.05		2	1			Noise									
11:48:00	1	0.04						Noise									
11:49:52																End of Run 5.1	
11:51:50																Start Run 5.2 @ FL330	
11:52:00	1	0.02						Noise									
11:54:00								Noise									
11:56:00	1	0.05	468	1	1	1		Noise									
11:58:00	6	0.03		5	2	5	100	Noise							11		
12:00:00	2	0.12	472	100	10	3	275	Noise							10		
12:02:00	1	0.12	473	10	10	30	100	Noise							11		
12:02:49																End of Run 5.2	
12:05:06																Start Run 5.3 @ FL330	
12:06:00	5	0.06	474	20	10	35	100	Noise							11		
12:08:00	5	0.06	476	100	10	60	200	Noise							10		
12:10:00	5	0.04	477	10	2	1	200	Noise							10		
12:12:00	10	0.06	478	5													
12:14:00	10	0.20	479	100	10	1		Noise								Our own contrail	
12:15:22																End of Run 5.3	
12:17:47																Start Profile 6 from FL330	
12:18:55	20	0.06	480	2	1			Noise								FL320	
12:20:03	20	0.07		2	1			Noise								FL310	
12:21:03	30	0.06		5	5	2	600	Noise							4	FL300	
12:22:15																End of Profile 6 & Start Run 6.1 @ FL290	
12:23:00	30	0.06	481	15	1	3	600	Noise							4		
12:25:00	40	0.06	486	30	1	3	600	Noise							4		
12:27:00	45	0.10		10	1	10	250	Noise							10		
12:29:00	30	0.10	488	70	10	15	100	Noise							11		
12:31:00	35	0.06	489	5	Noise			Noise									

PCASP Reference Volts = 9.3V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.4V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.17V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.0 cc/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.0V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.06V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 12mw	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = -3.2V		

# CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 326

Date: 07:15:00	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 4 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:32:18																End of Run 6.1	
12:34:30																Start Profile 7 from FL290	
12:35:42	10	0.06	490	10	10	25	150	Noise								FL280	
12:36:30	5	0.08		40	10	10	175	Noise								FL270	
12:37:29	20	0.06	491	10	10	7	75	Noise								FL260	
12:38:27	25	0.06	492	10	3	5	200	Noise								FL250	
12:39:30	20	0.11	493	15	2	25	500	Noise								FL240	
12:40:32																End of Profile 7 & Start Run 7.1 @ FL230	
12:41:00	10	0.06		1				Noise									
12:43:00	8	0.07		1	1			Noise									
12:45:00	4	0.11	494	40	3	1	300	Noise							10		
12:47:00	4	0.06		1				Noise									
12:49:00	2	0.06		2				Noise									
12:50:44																End of Run 7.1	
12:52:34																Start Run 7.2 @ FL230	
12:53:00	2	0.06	495	1	1			Noise									
12:55:00	2	0.06		2	1			Noise									
12:55:45																End of Run 7.2	
12:56:12																Start Orbits	
13:00:00																End Orbits	
Noise problems on PCASP and FFFSP on low level run at start due to Deimos																	
SID2 noisy at times																	
2D2-P noisy at high altitudes																	

PCASP Reference Volts = 9.3V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.4V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.17V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.0 cc/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.0V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.06V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 12mw	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = -3.2V		



B326_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

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07:04:35.20 --- - - - -
07:04:35.20 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
07:04:35.20 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                                tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
07:04:35.20 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B326
07:04:35.20 --- - - - -
07:04:50.42 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:05:07.27 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:05:18.20 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:05:40.24 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
07:05:44.43 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
07:05:47.32 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
07:06:12.50 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
07:06:16.66 SWS - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
07:06:21.34 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
07:06:25.10 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
07:06:29.07 LSH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 500ms.
07:06:32.36 LSH - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 500ms.
07:06:40.05 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:06:40.05 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:06:40.06 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:06:41.90 SWS - - - - Idling
07:06:42.49 USH - - - - Idling
07:06:44.67 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
07:06:46.22 LSH - - - - Idling
07:06:49.15 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:06:49.17 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:06:49.17 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:06:50.49 SWS - - - - Idling
07:06:50.60 USH - - - - Idling
07:06:54.81 LSH - - - - Idling
07:07:28.96 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:07:28.97 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:07:28.97 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:08:26.81 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:08:26.95 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:08:27.63 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:08:27.95 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:08:28.24 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:08:33.06 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:08:45.53 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:08:50.97 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:08:52.94 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
07:08:59.35 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:09:04.77 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:09:08.26 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:09:09.69 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:09:23.57 USH - - - - Idling
07:09:23.66 SWS - - - - Idling
07:09:24.40 LSH - - - - Idling
07:09:39.90 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:09:39.91 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:09:39.92 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:09:40.84 SWS - - - - Idling
07:09:41.75 USH - - - - Idling
07:09:45.55 LSH - - - - Idling
07:09:47.29 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:09:47.29 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:09:47.30 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:10:00.34 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:10:00.65 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:10:00.98 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:10:14.50 SWS - - - - Idling
07:10:14.59 USH - - - - Idling
07:10:14.78 LSH - - - - Idling
07:10:18.06 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:10:18.06 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.

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07:10:18.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:10:19.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:10:19.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:10:23.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:10:26.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:10:26.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:10:26.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:21:18.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:21:18.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:21:18.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:21:20.75	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:21:24.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:21:26.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:21:29.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:21:29.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:21:29.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:21:30.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:21:31.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:21:34.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:21:45.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:21:50.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:22:14.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:22:14.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:22:14.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:39:06.07	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 200ms.
08:39:11.33	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 200ms.
08:39:13.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:39:16.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:59:18.43	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
08:59:22.38	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
08:59:27.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:59:28.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:00:50.78	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:01:00.19	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
09:01:03.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:01:06.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:01:10.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:01:12.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:01:14.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:01:16.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:09:18.48	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
09:09:21.00	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
09:09:31.23	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:09:34.62	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:10:15.33	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:10:17.96	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:10:23.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:23.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:23.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:24.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:10:24.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:10:25.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:12:18.73	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
09:12:25.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:12:26.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:12:26.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:12:27.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:12:27.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:12:27.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:12:30.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:12:30.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:12:30.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:12:46.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start
09:13:32.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start P1 descent, from FL180
09:16:06.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** cirrus above, Sc below
09:25:33.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:25:36.58	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
09:25:39.32	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
09:25:40.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

09:25:41.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:25:43.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:26:27.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:26:31.32	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
09:26:34.87	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
09:26:36.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:26:39.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:26:40.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:04.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** End profile
09:32:39.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** really the end of profilr
09:32:45.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:45.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:45.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:46.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:47.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:48.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:50.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:50.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:50.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:50.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:59.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:33:09.79	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 200ms.
09:33:13.87	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 200ms.
09:33:17.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:33:17.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:33:17.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:33:18.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:33:19.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:33:19.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:33:22.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:33:22.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:33:22.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:33:28.63	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
09:35:21.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run 1.1 100'
09:39:11.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:39:11.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:39:11.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:39:12.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:39:13.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:39:14.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:57.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:43:00.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:43:02.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:43:11.06	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
09:43:16.43	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
09:43:19.34	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
09:43:22.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:43:23.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:43:26.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:45:24.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
09:45:31.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:45:31.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:45:31.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:45:32.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:45:32.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:45:33.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:45:35.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:47:15.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:47:40.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** start profile up
10:13:53.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profile FL240
10:13:59.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:59.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:59.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:14:00.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:01.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:14:02.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:46.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run 2.1
10:15:46.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:15:53.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

10:15:54.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:15:56.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:54.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** really start run 2.1, FL230
10:18:48.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:18:49.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:50.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:18:54.22	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
10:18:57.58	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
10:18:59.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:00.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:19:02.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:22:19.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:22:19.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:22:19.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:22:21.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:22:21.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:22:22.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:36.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:24:38.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:40.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:24:43.71	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
10:24:46.65	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
10:24:48.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:50.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:24:52.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:32.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:26:34.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:35.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:26:38.51	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
10:26:50.02	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:26:53.33	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:26:55.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:55.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:26:57.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:55.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
10:27:59.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:28:01.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:02.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:28:22.05	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
10:28:40.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:40.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:28:43.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:57.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run 2.2
10:34:02.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:34:02.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:34:02.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:34:03.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:04.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:04.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:25.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:37:27.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:28.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:37:30.13	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
10:37:39.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:40.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:37:42.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:46.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
10:39:52.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:39:53.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:39:54.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:40:05.88	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
10:40:10.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:10.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:10.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:11.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:40:11.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:12.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:18.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:39.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run 2.3

10:45:14.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:14.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:14.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:15.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:15.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:15.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:31.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:48:33.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:34.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:48:36.29	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
10:48:48.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:49.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:48:51.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:51:37.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
10:51:42.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:51:45.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:45.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:45.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:46.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:51:46.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:51:46.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:03.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:48.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** start orbit
10:53:57.96	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
10:55:27.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:55:31.87	SWS	-	-	5	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 5ms.
10:55:34.67	SWS	-	-	5	-	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 5ms.
10:55:36.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:36.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:55:39.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:36.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:59:05.89	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 10ms.
10:59:09.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:59:10.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:59:15.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:50.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:00:52.90	SWS	-	-	5	-	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 5ms.
11:00:57.91	SWS	-	-	10	-	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 10ms.
11:01:21.76	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
11:01:24.79	SWS	-	-	40	-	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 40ms.
11:01:27.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:28.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:01:31.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:33.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** start profile 3 from FL230
11:03:39.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:39.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:39.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:39.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:40.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:40.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:32.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** end p start run
11:05:59.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** fl250
11:09:50.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:50.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:50.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:51.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:52.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:52.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:38.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:10:40.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:40.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:10:41.93	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:10:50.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:50.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:10:53.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:02.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:13:05.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:06.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:13:14.17	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F

11:13:15.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:16.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:13:18.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:23.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
11:15:27.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:27.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:27.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:28.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:29.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:29.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:24.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** start profile to fl300
11:17:32.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:17:35.11	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 50ms.
11:17:37.72	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 50ms.
11:17:38.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:39.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:17:41.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:23:47.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** end p start run
11:23:51.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:23:53.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:23:54.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:24:01.53	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:24:04.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:04.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:27:06.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:07.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:27:09.21	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:27:18.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:07.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:29:09.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:10.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:29:11.57	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:29:19.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:45.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
11:30:47.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:30:47.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:30:47.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:30:48.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:49.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:49.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:33:54.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** start p
11:39:48.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** end p start run at fl330
11:39:51.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:51.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:51.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:52.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:53.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:53.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:18.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:18.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:18.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:19.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:20.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:20.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:45.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:46:47.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:48.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:46:49.22	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:47:01.72	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
11:47:03.92	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
11:47:05.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:07.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:47:09.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:49:51.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
11:49:55.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:55.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:55.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:56.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:49:56.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:49:56.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:08.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:50:18.27	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:50:22.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:24.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:50:26.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:41.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:41.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:41.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:43.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:43.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:43.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:51:48.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run fl330
11:54:48.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:48.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:48.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:49.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:49.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:49.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:58:00.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:58:02.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:58:03.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:58:03.81	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:58:19.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:58:20.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:58:23.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:00:02.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:00:04.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:06.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:00:07.13	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:00:25.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:48.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
12:02:51.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:51.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:51.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:52.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:53.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:53.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:22.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run
12:04:22.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:04:24.84	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:04:27.87	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:04:30.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:31.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:04:33.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:05.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** really start run at fl330
12:09:52.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:52.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:52.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:53.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:53.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:54.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:12:37.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:12:39.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:12:40.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:12:40.82	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:12:55.05	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
12:12:58.35	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
12:13:00.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:01.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:13:09.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:15:23.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
12:15:26.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:15:26.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:15:26.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:15:27.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:15:27.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:15:28.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:15:28.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

12:15:29.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:15:42.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:15:42.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:15:42.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:15:43.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:15:44.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:15:44.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:15:45.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:15:46.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:15:46.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:15:46.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:15:51.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:15:52.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:15:52.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:48.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** start profile down
12:22:15.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profile start run
12:24:28.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:28.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:28.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:30.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:30.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:30.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:47.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:24:49.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:49.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:49.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:51.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:51.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:51.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:25:00.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:22.62	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:27:55.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:27:56.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:56.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:56.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:56.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:58.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:58.14	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:27:58.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:27:58.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:13.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:13.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:13.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:14.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:14.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:15.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:28:16.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:17.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:31:14.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:31:16.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:31:16.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:31:16.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:31:17.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:31:18.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:31:18.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:31:23.75	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:31:27.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:31:40.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:31:44.26	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:31:47.21	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:31:49.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:31:50.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:31:52.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:32:21.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
12:32:26.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:26.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:26.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:26.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:27.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

12:32:28.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:32:28.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:33.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:32:33.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:32:33.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:32:37.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:37.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:37.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:38.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:32:38.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:32:39.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:32:41.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:32:41.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:32:42.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:33:28.54	---	-	-	-	-	***
12:33:28.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:33:33.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:34.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:33:35.75	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:33:49.84	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
12:33:52.27	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
12:33:54.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:55.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:33:57.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:34:24.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** start p
12:40:20.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** end p start r fl230
12:40:20.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:20.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:20.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:21.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:21.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:22.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:43:36.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:43:39.29	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:43:42.29	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:43:44.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:45.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:43:47.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:44:09.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:44:09.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:44:09.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:44:11.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:44:11.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:44:11.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:47:02.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:47:04.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:04.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:04.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:05.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:47:05.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:47:05.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:47:08.54	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:47:27.65	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
12:47:30.26	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
12:47:32.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:33.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:47:35.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:50:45.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
12:50:53.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:50:53.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:50:53.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:50:54.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:50:54.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:50:54.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:50:58.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:51:06.08	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:51:25.10	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:51:28.43	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:51:31.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

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12:51:32.10 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:51:34.60 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:52:33.47 --- - - - - *** start run fl230
12:55:54.78 --- - - - - *** end run start orbit
12:57:55.94 LSH - - - - Idling
12:57:55.94 USH - - - - Idling
12:57:55.96 SWS - - - - Idling
12:57:57.59 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:57.59 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:57.60 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:58.53 SWS - - - - Idling
12:57:59.23 LSH - - - - Idling
12:57:59.43 USH - - - - Idling
12:58:01.30 SWS - - 10 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 10ms.
12:58:04.54 SWS - - - 10 - NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 10ms.
12:58:07.57 USH - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
12:58:10.00 USH - - - 75 - NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
12:58:11.84 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:58:11.85 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:58:11.85 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:58:13.30 SWS - - - - Idling
12:58:14.01 USH - - - - Idling
12:58:14.11 LSH - - - - Idling
12:58:16.19 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:58:16.19 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:58:16.21 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:00:06.39 SWS - - - - Idling
13:00:06.40 LSH - - - - Idling
13:00:06.42 USH - - - - Idling
13:00:07.62 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:00:07.63 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:00:07.63 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:00:08.16 SWS - - - - Idling
13:00:09.80 USH - - - - Idling
13:00:09.82 LSH - - - - Idling
13:00:11.51 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:00:11.52 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:00:11.52 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:00:17.91 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:00:21.86 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
13:00:26.22 SWS - - - 100 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
13:00:28.47 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:00:29.91 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:00:31.97 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:02:12.94 --- - - - - *** end of science
13:02:15.31 USH - - - - Idling
13:02:15.31 SWS - - - - Idling
13:02:15.33 LSH - - - - Idling
13:02:17.41 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:02:17.41 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:02:17.42 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:02:18.85 SWS - - - - Idling
13:02:19.00 USH - - - - Idling
13:02:19.05 LSH - - - - Idling
13:02:22.36 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:02:22.37 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:02:22.39 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

```

240  
 3 = 360  
 4 = 480

# ARIES flight log

Flight: 826

page 1 of 3

Date: 12/09/07

Operator(s): Joss Kerr

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes: S/W Approaches

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
0700	Started	Ascii	Housekeeping	Acquisition			
072900	Grnd	1/120	HBB	Clso	7115		Ground cal for brightnesses
073038	Grnd	1/120	CBS	Clso	3359		
085839	FL180	1/60 1/60	CAL	Clso	7112	3128	CBS/HBB
091202	FL180	1/60	CAL	Clso	7064	3084	
091329	FL180	BBO	Zen	open			Start of Profile.
091446	<del>FL</del>	1/60	CAL	Clso			
	<del>100'</del>						
093335	100'	1/60	CAL	Clso	7087	3065	CAL in turn @ low level
093504	100'	480	Ncd	Clso	7093	715	
093509	100'	7/60	CAL	Clso	7067	3050	
094027	100'	360	Ncd	Clso			
094334	100'	120	Zen	open			Imiduck only
094448	100'	1/60x2	CAL	Clso	7068	3104	Using script cal/Hor CAL
101328	FL240	" "	CAL	Clso	7087	3073	
101437	" "	" "	" "	" "	7067	3084	In turn
		<del>1/60x2</del>	<del>Zen</del>	<del>open</del>			
101708	<del>FL230</del>	1/60x2	CAL	Clso	7083	3051	Cal script.
101824	FL230	480/1	Zen	open	7063	3058	
102225	FL230	1/60x2	CAL	Clso	7083	3045	Cal script 30 sec, 50 sec
102340	FL230	360x1	Zen	open	7112	3053	3manue
102650	<del>FL230</del>	<del>1/60x1</del>	<del>Ncd</del>	<del>Clso</del>			
102711	FL230	180/1	Ncd	Clso			102904 End Ncd in view
102819	FL230	1/60x2	CAL	Clso	7066	3029	
102955	FL230	1/60x2	CAL	Clso	7092	3048	
103111	FL230	360x1	open	Zen			
103412	FL230	1/60x2	Clso	CAL			
107526	FL230	240/1	Zen	open	7092	301	
103735	FL230	240/1	Ncd	Clso	7048	3024	
103941	FL230	1/60x2	Cal	Clso	7044	3108	
104009	FL230	1/60x2	CAL	Clso	7057	3086	

# ARIES flight log

Flight: B326

page 2 of 3

Date: 12/09/07

Operator(s): Joss Kern

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: S/W Approaches CAESAR

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
104204	FL230	360x1	Zen	open			Some structure in Corvus
104565	FL230	<del>1/60</del> 2x2	cal	clsd	70-82	30-07	
104620	FL230	<del>360</del> x1	Zen	open			
104856	FL230	240 x1	Nwd	clsd	70-7	30-79	
105110	FL230	1/60 x1	cal	clsd	70-67	30-52	
105333	FL230	360/1	Zen	open	70-78	30-15	50° banking orbiter ended 115936
105554	FL230	360/1	Zen	open			" " "
105832	FL230	<del>60</del> 1/60	cal	clsd	71-16	31-5	cal didn't finish program end 110050
110026	FL230	360/1	Zen	open			Cor hung up on 60° orbiter
110110	FL230	cal	cal	clsd	70-91	30-71	
110523	FL250	cal	cal	clsd	70-5	30-46	
110646	FL250	360/1	Zen	open			
110940	FL250	cal	cal	clsd	70-91	30-76	
111051	FL250	240/1	Nwd	clsd	70-75	30-51	
111259	FL250	240/1	Zen	open			
111501	FL250	1/60	cal	clsd	70-78	29-7	
112367	FL300	1/60	cal	clsd	70-84	30-51	
112564	FL300	240/1	Nwd	clsd			Still some corvus above.
112708	FL300	240/1	Zen	open			
112917	FL300	240/1	Nwd	clsd			
113053	FL300	1/60 x2	cal	clsd	70-76	30-10	
113900	FL325	1/60 x2	cal	clsd	70-68	30-97	
114015	FL330	800/1	Nwd	clsd	70-62	30-41	
114308	FL330	1/60 x2	cal	clsd	70-76	30-71	
114449	FL330	320/1	Nwd	clsd	70-6	30-51	Clear of Corvus above.
114704	FL330	800/1	Zen	open			
114912	FL330	1/60 x2	cal	clsd	70-83	30-99	
115023	FL330	1/60 x2	cal	clsd	70-60	30-84	
115147	FL330	<del>360</del> 3	Nwd	clsd	70-60	30-67	
115449	FL330	1/60 x2	cal	clsd	70-71	30-72	
115599	FL330	240/1	Nwd	clsd			

115806 FL330 240/1 Zen open

# ARIES flight log

Flight: 13226

page 3 of 3

Date: 12/09/07

Operator(s): Joss Kent.

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: Slw Approaches

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Comments
<del>120032</del>							
120032	FL330	651/160	cal	clsd	7081	304	
120142	FL330	240/1	Nad	clsd			ended 120254
120427	FL330		cal	clsd	7064	3042	
120543	FL330	360/1	Nad	clsd			
120850	FL330	1/60	cal	clsd	7067	3049	
121010	FL330	300/1	Nad	clsd			
121244	FL330	300/1	Zen	open			
121521	FL330	1/60	cal	clsd	7050	3065	
122054	FL295	cal		clsd	7077	3089	
122216	FL290	Zen 240/1		open	7051	3036	
	FL290	240/1	Nad	clsd			In cloud run
<del>122428</del>							
122542	FL290	240	Nad	clsd			
122750	FL290	1/60	cal	clsd	7049	3061	
122907	FL290	240	Zen	open			
123113	FL290	240	Nad	clsd			Ended @ 123222
123236	FL290	1/60 x2	cal	clsd	7084	3031	
123917	FL240	1/60 x2	cal	clsd	7051	3016	
124036	FL230	480/1	Zen	open	7016	3019	
124406	FL230	1/60 x2	cal	clsd	7112	3021	
124517	FL230	240/1	Zen	open	7056	3011	
124723	FL230	240/1	Nad	clsd			
124925	FL230	1/60 x2	cal	clsd	7068	3076	
125130	FL230	1/60 x2	cal	clsd	7054	3048	
125245	FL230	480/1	Zen	open			
		1/60 x2	cal				
125611	FL230		Zen	open			Onbort 50°
125809	FL230		Zen	open			Onbort 50° ended 130004
130004	FL230	1/60 x2	cal	clsd	7074	3043	
130504	Stopped because of acquisition						

<b>Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG</b>		Date	12/09/07	Flight	B326	log pages
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	CAESAR		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield		

**System start  
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						X
FERA on				at time	06:56:33	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	19°C	Ch	19°C	Ch18	18°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on				at time	06:57:06	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	289.7	Cold		286.9	
Target heating						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X
Scanning on (LMD box)				at time	07:01:15	
Scan indication		Monitor	)		Visual	X

**Deimos**

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						X
Turn on Deimos CPU						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X
Start Deimos Software				at time	07:03:53	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	289.9	Cold		289.0	
Target heating						X
Scan indication		Monitor	)		Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

**System functionality check** (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$			at time		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						X
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.6	Cold	288.0	
	Deimos:	Hot	344.9	Cold	295.9	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	47.99	41.15	54.10	40.77		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	39.19	31.67	39.55	42.01	42.93	

**Power changeover**

Headset on before start				
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.			
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)				
Exit Deimos Software (x)				
<b>POWER CHANGEOVER</b>				
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton			
Restart Deimos Software				
System running again			at time	



B326

security 0845 L  
T/O 0930 L  
land 1445 L

WOW  
INLU  
GIN  
NEPH  
PSAP  
ASP  
HEIMANN  
BBR.

To Cranfield  
08:32:31



land Cranfield.  
135249

# Flight:

# B326

**KEY**

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

### Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

### Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

### Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

### Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

**Report Created 11/10/2007  
17:35:23**

### Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

### Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

**Last Updated:**

### Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

**11/10/2007 09:16:21**

### Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:



## Faults / Incidents Log

**Flight No. B326**

**Date: 12/09/2007**

### Instruments

1. HORACE optical disc failure on pre-flight. Disc labelled and replaced by serviceable unit.
2. FM pc crash and restart
3. ISDN link – no connection throughout flight

### Aircraft

nil

### Satcom-H Calls

Nil

### Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

## Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 12/09/07

Flight No: B326

Pre-Flighter: SWH.

No.	<input type="checkbox"/> or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<b><u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u></b>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	<del>Be Dead.</del>
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
<b>Proceed to External Checks</b>				
External Checks overleaf <span style="float: right;">→</span>				

## Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>No.</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<b><u>External Checks</u></b>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<b><u>Avalon Checks</u></b>				Signed
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
46	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		N/A.

## MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B326:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
TAFTS	TAFTS operator does not create a log sheet

## Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	7 Jan 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

## VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Upward Facing Cameras  
1 x For/Downward Facing Cameras  
2 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Stuart Newman

Met Office  
Cordouan 2 W078  
FitzRoy Road  
Devon  
EX1 3PB  
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 884605

E-mail: [stu.newman@metoffice.gov.uk](mailto:stu.newman@metoffice.gov.uk)